

Oxidation of 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde by alkaline *N*-bromosuccinimide – A kinetic and mechanistic study

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Abstract : The kinetics of the oxidation of 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde (2-HNA) by *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS) in aqueous alkaline medium at a constant ionic strength of 0.60 mol dm⁻³ was studied titrimetrically. The reaction is of first order in [NBS] and of fractional order in both [2-HNA] and [alkali]. Addition of products has no significant effect on the reaction rate. However, increasing ionic strength and decreasing dielectric constant of the medium increases the rate. The oxidation process in alkaline medium has been shown to proceed via the formation of a complex between the active species of the oxidant and the substrate followed by the decomposition of the complex in a slow rate determining step to yield the product. Some reaction constants involved in the mechanism were determined. The calculated and observed rate constants agree excellently. The activation parameters were computed with respect to the slow step of the mechanism.

Keywords : 2-Hydroxynaphthaldehyde, *N*-bromosuccinimide, kinetics, oxidation.

Introduction

A large numbers of *N*-halides (or imides) including some *N*-fluoro compounds, have since been prepared and tested as reagents for allylic bromination and oxidation of organic compounds. Only a few of these compounds have been found to have distinct advantages for routine work, while others remains of academic interest only. The only reagent which have been found to have as wide acceptability as NBS for allylic bromination are the *N*-bromohydantoin. However, some of the reagents which were found to be poor allylic brominating reagents have proved to be better reagents in certain other reactions, particularly those involving the use of polar medium and where the reaction proceeds by an ionic rather than a free radical mechanism. *N*-Bromosuccinimide and *N*-chlorosuccinimide for example, have proved to be stronger oxidants.

N-Bromosuccinimide is a source of positive halogen, and this reagent has been exploited¹ as oxidant for a variety of substances in both acidic and alkaline medium. The use of *N*-bromosuccinimide as an oxidant in acidic medium is extensive² and it has also been used in the

determination of some organic compounds³. This potent oxidizing agent has chiefly been restricted to the oxidometric determination of several compounds⁴. This prompted us to undergo kinetics and mechanistic investigation.

2-Hydroxynaphthaldehyde (2-HNA) is a source of many organic compounds and it is also used in the chromatographic determination of some amino acids. It has got applications in synthetic and pharmaceutical chemistry. Although a variety of organic⁵ and inorganic⁶ substrates are oxidised by *N*-bromosuccinimide.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry and product analysis : Different sets of reaction mixtures containing different amounts of reactants at constant alkalinity and ionic strength were allowed to react for 24 h in a closed container where [NBS] > [2-HNA]. The remaining *N*-bromosuccinimide was assayed iodometrically⁷. The results showed a ratio of consumption of oxidant to reductant of 1 : 1 as given in eq. (1).

The main oxidation products identified were 2-hydroxynaphthylidic acid⁸ and succinimide⁹ by their respective spot tests. Further the existence of 2-hydroxynaphthylidic acid was confirmed by its IR spectrum which showed a carbonyl (C=O) stretching at 1639 cm⁻¹, OH⁻ stretching at 2792 cm⁻¹ and -OH (due to hydrogen bonding) stretching at 3463 cm⁻¹.

Reaction order :

The kinetic runs of oxidation of 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde by *N*-bromosuccinimide in aqueous alkaline medium were followed at different initial concentrations of oxidant, substrate and alkali keeping all other concentrations constant. The reaction orders were determined from the slopes of log *k*_{obs} versus log concentration plots.

Effect of [*N*-bromosuccinimide] : The oxidant, [NBS] was varied in the range of 2.0 × 10⁻⁴ to 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ (Table 1) and the linearity of plots of log [NBS] versus time indicates the order in [NBS] as unity. This was also confirmed by varying [NBS] which did not show any change in pseudo-first order rate constants, *k*_{obs}.

Effect of [2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde] : The concentration of substrate, 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde was varied in the concentration range of 5.0 × 10⁻³ to 5.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ at 27 °C keeping all other [reactants] constant (Table 1). The order in [2-HNA] was found to be less than unity.

Table 1. Effect of variation of [NBS], [2-HNA] and [OH⁻] on the oxidation of 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde by *N*-bromosuccinimide in aqueous alkaline medium at 27 °C

I = 0.60 mol dm⁻³

10 ³ [NBS] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ² [2-HNA] (mol dm ⁻³)	[OH ⁻] (mol dm ⁻³)	<i>k</i> _{obs} × 10 ³	
			Expt.	Calcd.
0.2	1.0	0.10	1.22	1.22
0.4	1.0	0.10	1.23	1.22
1.0	1.0	0.10	1.21	1.22
1.5	1.0	0.10	1.23	1.22
2.0	1.0	0.10	1.22	1.22
0.2	0.5	0.10	0.86	0.88
0.4	1.0	0.10	1.21	1.22
1.0	2.0	0.10	1.75	1.77
1.5	3.0	0.10	1.83	1.83
2.0	5.0	0.10	2.16	2.15
0.2	0.5	0.05	0.90	0.91
0.4	1.0	0.10	1.18	1.17
1.0	2.0	0.20	1.68	1.68
1.5	3.0	0.40	1.86	1.87
2.0	5.0	0.50	2.19	2.18

Effect of [alkali] : The effect of alkali on the reaction was studied at constant [2-HNA] and [NBS] keeping constant ionic strength of 0.60 mol dm⁻³ at 27 °C. The rate constant was increased with the increase in [OH⁻] (Table 1). The order with respect to alkali was found to be less than unity.

Effect of ionic strength : The effect of ionic strength was studied by varying the concentration of NaClO₄ from 0.6 to 2.0 mol dm⁻³ other conditions being constant. It has been observed that the rate of reaction increases while increasing the [NaClO₄] (Table 1). The plot of log *k*_{obs} versus *I*_{1/2} gives straight line with positive slope (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Effect of variation of ionic strength (*I*) and solvent polarity on the oxidation 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde by *N*-bromosuccinimide in aqueous alkaline medium at 27 °C.

Dielectric constant : The dielectric constant (*D*) of the reaction medium was studied by varying the *t*-butanol-water (Baker sample) content in the reaction mixture from 1 to 10%. Attempts to measure the relative permittivity (*D*) were failed. However, they were computed from the values of pure liquids as in earlier work. The plot of log *k*_{obs} versus 1/*D*, where *D* is the dielectric constant of the medium gave straight line with negative slope (Fig. 1).

Earlier the inertness of the *t*-butanol towards the oxidant in the reaction mixture had been confirmed. With the increase of *t*-butanol content from 1 to 10% (v/v), the rate of reaction decreases.

Effect of initially added products : The initially added products such as succinimide and 2-hydroxynaphthylidic acid were studied between the concentration range 0.4 × 10⁻³ to 4.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³. The product 2-

hydroxynaphthalic acid has no significant effect on the rate of the reaction. However, another product, succinimide increases the rate of the reaction considerably.

Test for free radicals : The reaction mixture, to which a known amount of acrylonitrile scavenger had been added initially, was kept for 24 h in an inert atmosphere. On diluting the reaction mixture with methanol, a white precipitate was obtained indicating the presence of free radical intervention in the reaction.

Effect of temperature : The rate of reaction was measured at five different temperatures under varying [2-HNA]. The rate constants, k of the slow step of Scheme 1 were obtained from the intercept of plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[2\text{-HNA}]$ and $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{OH}^-]$ (Fig. 2). The data is subjected to least square analysis (Table 2). From the plot of $\log k$ versus $1/T$, the activation parameters have been calculated : E_a , $58 \pm 2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$; ΔH^\ddagger , $46 \pm 2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$; ΔG^\ddagger , $62 \pm 2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and ΔS^\ddagger , $-166 \pm 8 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

Fig. 2a. Verification of rate law (4) in the form of (6) for the oxidation of 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde by *N*-bromosuccinimide in aqueous alkaline medium : (conditions as in Table 1).

Fig. 2b. Verification of rate law (4) in the form of (6) for the oxidation of 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde by *N*-bromosuccinimide in aqueous alkaline medium : (conditions as in Table 1).

It has been known that the probable reactive species of *N*-bromosuccinimide in acid¹⁰ solutions are :

And the reactive species in alkaline¹¹ solutions are

In alkaline solutions in the absence of mercuric acetate it is likely that the oxidant exists as OBr^- and the order of less than unity in [2-HNA] reveals the possibility of involvement of complex formation in the reaction system. Attempts to obtain spectral evidence were in vain, and there was no appreciable change in the spectra of [2-HNA] and [NBS] in presence of alkali. A feeble interaction is probably involved. However, evidence for complex formation is obtained kinetically by the plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[2\text{-HNA}]$ which shows a positive intercept. Such complex formation between oxidant and substrate was observed in earlier studies¹².

Mechanism : The reaction exhibits 1 : 1 stoichiometry and first order each in [NBS] and [2-HNA]. Increase in rate with increase in $[\text{OH}^-]$ may be explained by assuming the following equilibrium

Table 2. Effect of temperature on the slow step of the mechanism of oxidation of 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde by alkaline *N*-bromosuccinimide

T (K)	(Conditions as in Table 1)			
	$k \times 10^3$ (s^{-1})	$1/T \times 10^3$ (K^{-1})	$\log k$ Y	$Y_{\text{Calcd.}}$
300	2.0	3.33	-2.68	-2.679
305	2.6	3.28	-2.53	-2.5301
310	3.7	3.23	-2.38	-2.379
315	4.8	3.18	-2.09	-2.092

Taking all the experimental result in to consideration, a mechanism as in Scheme 1 may be proposed.

Scheme 1

The active species of the oxidant reacts with the substrate, 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde to form a complex with the equilibrium constant K_2 . The complex decomposes in a rate determining step to give free radical of 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde and succinimide, which further yield 2-hydroxynaphthalic acid.

The probable structure of the complex (C) is

Scheme 1 leads to the rate law (2)

$$\text{Rate} = -\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = \frac{kK_1K_2[2\text{-HNA}][\text{NBS}][\text{OH}^-]}{1 + K_1[\text{OH}^-] + K_1K_2[2\text{-HNA}][\text{OH}^-]} \times \frac{1}{(1 + K_1K_2[\text{NBS}][\text{OH}^-])(1 + K_1[\text{NBS} + K_1K_2[2\text{-HNA}][\text{NBS}])} \quad (2)$$

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = \frac{[\text{NBS}]_T kK_1K_2[2\text{-HNA}][\text{NBS}][\text{OH}^-]}{(1 + K_1K_2[\text{NBS}][\text{OH}^-])(1 + K_1[\text{NBS} + K_1K_2[2\text{-HNA}][\text{NBS}]) (1 + K_1[\text{OH}^-] + K_1K_2[2\text{-HNA}][\text{OH}^-])} \quad (3)$$

The term $(1 + K_1K_2[\text{NBS}][\text{OH}^-])$ and $(1 + K_1[\text{NBS} + K_1K_2[2\text{-HNA}][\text{NBS}])$ in the denominator of eq. (3) is approximated to unity in view of low concentration of NBS used. Thus, eq. (3) becomes eq. (4).

$$\text{Rate} = -\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = \frac{kK_1K_2[2\text{-HNA}][\text{NBS}][\text{OH}^-]}{1 + K_1[\text{OH}^-] + K_1K_2[2\text{-HNA}][\text{OH}^-]} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{NBS}]_T} = k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{kK_1K_2[2\text{-HNA}][\text{OH}^-]}{1 + K_1[\text{OH}^-] + K_1K_2[2\text{-HNA}][\text{OH}^-]} \quad (5)$$

Eq. (5) may be rearranged to the form (6) which is suitable for verification.

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{kK_1K_2[2\text{-HNA}][\text{OH}^-]} + \frac{1}{kK_2[2\text{-HNA}]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (6)$$

According to eq. (6) the plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[2\text{-HNA}]$ and $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{OH}^-]$ are expected to be linear (Fig. 2). The slope and intercept of such plot lead to the values of k and K_1 and K_2 as $5.22 \pm 0.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $2.19 \pm 0.1 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $1.64 \pm 0.08 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. These constants are used to calculate the rate constants over different experimental conditions. There is a good agreement between calculated and observed rate constants (Table 1).

The effect of increasing ionic strength on the rate qualitatively explains the reaction between the two negatively charged ions as shown in Scheme 1. However, increasing the content of *t*-butanol in the reaction medium leads to an increase of the reaction rate which is in contrary to the expected slower reaction between ions of a same polarity in media of lower relative permittivity. Perhaps the effect is opposed substantially by an increased formation of active reaction species in low permittivity media, thus leading to the observed net increase in the rate¹³.

The values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger were both favorable for electron transfer processes. The value of ΔS^\ddagger within the range for radical reaction, have been ascribed to the nature of electron pairing and unpairing process and to the loss of degree of freedom formerly available to the reactants upon the formation of rigid transition state¹⁴.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade chemicals. Doubly distilled water was used throughout this work. Stock solution of *N*-bromosuccinimide was prepared by dissolving a known amount of *N*-bromosuccinimide (Riedel) in water. The concentration of the solution was verified by titrating against standard sodium thiosulphate iodometrically³ using starch as an indicator. The substrate, 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde was prepared in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ NaOH. The succinimide was prepared¹⁵ and recrystallised by a known method as follows : A known amount of succinic acid is taken in to a round bottomed flask and concentrated ammonia solution was added slowly with cooling and shaking. Most of the acid dissolves forming a clear solution of ammonium succinate. The mixture was heated gently with a free flame and then strongly. The ammonium succinate commences to decompose with the evolution of ammonia and succinimide was collected in the flask. The crude succinimide was crystallised. Its solution was prepared by dissolving a known amount of succinimide in distilled water.

Sodium thiosulphate (Fischer) was prepared in water. It was standardised¹⁶ against potassium iodate. Sodium perchlorate which was found to be inactive was used to maintain constant ionic strength and perchloric acid (B.D.H.) was used to get the required alkalinity.

A regression analysis of experimental data, in order to obtain the regression coefficient (*r*) and the standard deviation (*s*), of points from the regression line, was performed with a computer Pentium IV processor.

Kinetic procedure : All kinetic measurements were performed under pseudo-first order conditions at 27 ± 0.1 °C unless stated otherwise. The reaction was initiated by mixing previously thermostated solutions of *N*-bromosuccinimide and 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde which also contained the required amount of NaOH and NaClO₄ to maintain the required alkalinity and ionic strength respectively. Here the concentration of hydroxyl ion was calculated considering the sodium hydroxide in 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde as well as the sodium hydroxide additionally added. The course of reaction was followed by determining the concentration of unreacted *N*-bromosuccinimide in aliquots (5 ml each) of the reaction mixture by titrating against standard sodium thiosulphate at neutral pH maintained by dihydrogen phosphate⁹. Such titrations were carried out at regular intervals.

The reaction was generally followed over a period

longer than three half lives. The first order rate constants were obtained from the slopes of log [NBS] versus time plots. The rate constants were reproducible to within ± 5%. The effect of dissolved oxygen on the rate of the reaction was checked by preparing the reaction mixture and following the reaction in a nitrogen atmosphere. There are no significant changes in the results obtained in the presence of nitrogen and in the presence of air.

In view of the ubiquitous contamination of carbonate in basic solutions, the effect of carbonate on the reaction was studied. Added carbonate showed no effect on the reaction rate. However, fresh solutions were used while conducting the experiments.

Conclusion : The reaction between *N*-bromosuccinimide and 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde in alkaline medium has a stoichiometry of 1 : 1 with first order dependence on [NBS] and fractional order both in [2-HNA] and [OH⁻]. Among various species of [NBS] in alkaline medium, a mechanism has been proposed with OBr⁻ as the active oxidant species.

Addition of one of the product, succinimide, increases the rate of the reaction. However, another product such as 2-hydroxynaphthalic acid does not effect the rate. The effect of increasing ionic strength on the rate qualitatively explains the reaction between two neutral ions as shown in Scheme 1. However, increasing the content of *t*-butanol in the reaction mixture leads to an increase on the reaction rate which is in contrary to the expected slower reaction between ions of same polarity in media of lower relative permittivity. Perhaps the effect opposed substantially by an increased active reaction species in low permittivity media, thus leading to the observed net increase in the rate. The values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger were both favorable for electron transfer process. The values of ΔS^\ddagger , within the range for radical reaction, have been ascribed to the nature of electron pairing and unpairing processes and to the loss of degree of freedom formerly available to the reactants upon the formation of a rigid transition state.

Investigation at different temperatures allowed the determination of the activation parameters with respect to slow step of the proposed mechanism.

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